

INTERPLAY OF LIBRARIANS' REGULATORY AWARENESS, SERVICE DELIVERY, TYPE OF INSTITUTION AND FACULTY'S LIBRARY UTILIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Academic libraries play an important role in supporting instructional processes in higher education, especially when institutions transition to digital learning environments and comply with CHED Memorandum Order No. 22, Series of 2021. This study examined the relationship between librarians' regulatory awareness and service delivery implementation, as well as their impact on faculty members' use of library services for instructional support. A descriptive-correlational research approach was used with 20 librarians and 137 faculty members from selected higher education institutions in Surigao del Norte. The data were gathered using validated survey questionnaires and analyzed using weighted mean, Pearson correlation, analysis of variance, and independent samples t-test. Faculty members' overall utilization of library services was moderate, with instructional enhancement emerging as the most commonly used attribute. The analysis of variance revealed substantial differences in faculty consumption of instructional enhancement services based on the level of service delivery implementation. Furthermore, independent samples t-test results revealed that teacher utilization was higher in private colleges than in public institutions. These findings indicate that institutional type has a major impact on faculty engagement, emphasizing the importance of public higher education institutions improving resources, services, digital infrastructure, and faculty-librarian collaboration to increase instructional use of library services.

Keywords: *regulatory awareness, service delivery, faculty utilization, institution, academic libraries, CMO No. 22*

INTRODUCTION

In today's world, academic libraries are vital components of the educational system, as they contribute significantly to the research and instruction. The educational scene is fast converging the digital age, which compels libraries to keep pace in terms of developing the services needed by the library users. Due to technological advancements libraries create new routes of education, causing the academe to adapt. As a result, libraries must alter their services to meet the needs of library user working both on and off campus.

According to Marigondon (2025), librarians' regulatory awareness is essential for complying with CHED Memorandum Order No. 22, s. 2021 accreditation standards in administration, collection management, and IT infrastructure. These guidelines focus on improving library services through effective collection management, IT development, physical facilities, and institutional linkages. Libraries are expected to promote digital resources and remote access while following metadata standards such as MARC21 and Dublin Core. Compliance ensures that the facilities, resources, and services available within the library will be aligned with the requirements of teaching and research activities, leading to an increase in faculty use. Compliance will ultimately lead to an increase in faculty use and improved academic performance.

Furthermore, libraries provide faculty resources to enhance instruction, integrating technology, and increasing library utilization (Wheeler et al., 2022). This occurs through accessible resources and training programs for effective utilization. Despite the guidelines of CHED Memorandum Order No. 22, s. 2021, a crucial concern remains whether librarians are sufficiently aware of these standards, and how this affects service implementation and faculty utilization. Policy mandates are routinely neglected, leaving gaps in compliance and service delivery (Ifijeh & Yusuf, 2020). Challenges include insufficient professional development, inadequate institutional communication, and fast policy changes (Shafack & Mbeng, 2021). Libraries face stagnation and failure to fulfill standards in a digitally driven educational environment if sufficient awareness is not raised.

This research is associated with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4) with respect to the Sustainable Development Goals and is focused on the promotion of inclusive and equitable quality education with accompanying lifelong learning opportunities for all. The study hypothesized that library service improvement in alliance with better policy 3 compliance would strengthen the instruction support of higher education institutions meeting Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) objectives towards quality education. It enables libraries to open up learning spaces to students, faculty members, and others through upgrading library materials based on faculty suggestions, using digital technology for the services, and delivering targeted information and digital literacy training.

The review of literature and studies had a direct bearing on the present study, as these provide a comprehensive and in-depth view of regulatory awareness among academic librarians, particularly concerning CHED Memorandum Order No. 22, Series of 2021,

which is significant in shaping the direction and quality of academic library services. The mandate of CMO No. 22 s 2021 is for libraries to maintain high-quality, accessible, and dynamic collections that support both onsite and online, technology-driven learning environments. Librarians who understand these regulations can review and improve their collections to meet curricular and research needs. This regulatory strategy has led libraries to integrate services, add digital and open-access resources, and adapt their spaces and services to meet the demands of post-pandemic schooling.

Overall, the ideas referenced in this study established a solid foundation and made a more substantial contribution to this study. Thus, this relates to the primary variable of the present study, which is to measure the regulatory awareness of librarians as to CHED Memo No. 22 s 2021, the service delivery implementation, and the level of faculty utilization for instructional enhancement to demonstrate an increase in work productivity that would result in the highest quality of service for academic libraries in Surigao Del Norte.

Hence, the study aims to evaluate the implementation of service delivery, the level of awareness of librarians' awareness of CMO No. 22 s. 2021, and how these variables had affected faculty utilization of library resources in improving education in Higher Education Institution in Surigao Del Norte. Moreover, the goal of this study was to evaluate the implementation that promote effective collaboration between librarians and faculty members, thereby helping bridge the existing research gaps and supporting efforts to improve the collaboration of the librarians and faculty yielding a more enabling and innovative learning environment aligned with national educational goals and global development targets.

This study assumed that librarians' regulatory awareness and service delivery significantly associated with faculty library utilization. This assumption is anchored on Organizational Change Theory (Gwaka et al., 2020) and Three Stage Model of change by Errida and Lotfi's (2021), as well as Kurt Lewin's (1947) change framework. These theories explain how organization awareness, implementation, and institutionalization of change. 4 In the context of this study, these frameworks were relevant in understanding how libraries comply with CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 22, series of 2021, and how such compliance shapes service delivery and faculty library utilization.

Research Questions

1. What is the frequency and average number of citations used in the MLIS theses from 2019 to 2025?
2. What is the distributional profile of cited references based on material format (e.g., journals, books, web resources)?
3. What is the recency of sources cited in the MLIS theses according to the year of publication?
4. Which indexing databases are most frequently utilized by MLIS graduate students for their citations?
5. What is the geographic distribution of cited sources in terms of local and foreign origins?

METHODOLOGY

The participants of the study were the 20 library personnel and the 137 faculty members of private and public higher education institutions in Surigao City and Surigao Del Norte, that were considered appropriate stakeholders in the provision and utilization of library services for instructional enhancement. Faculty members represented the side of demand, being the main users of library resources for teaching and curriculum support; whereas the librarians represented the side of supply in implementing regulatory mandates and delivering service. Thus, the two perspectives gave a composite view of how enlightenment on regulation and library services affect faculty utilization. The inclusion of both a private and a public higher education institution, as well as different campuses further ensured the diversity and improved the representativeness and generalizability of the results of this study in the context of higher education in the province.

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational approach through a survey technique. This research design aimed to examine and describe the relationship between different variables in a way that is not a cause-and-effect relationship. This research design was helpful in measuring the degree of association between two variables, and it additionally enables the formulation of informed predictions (Bhandari, 2021). This design was appropriate for this study as it directly supported the objectives of describing current practices and examining the relationships among variables without inferring causality. Therefore, measuring librarians' regulatory awareness and service delivery against the faculty members' utilization of library services for instructional support allowed the research establishing the degree of association between these two factors. This was done through the survey that helped in retrieving more actual data from a large group of participants thus, giving a good and generalizable understanding of how regulatory awareness and library services are associated with faculty instructional practices.

Furthermore, the participants were selected with the use of two sampling methods. For the library personnel, the study employed total enumeration sampling, wherein 20 library personnel, were all included in the study in order to provide for a representative population directly concerned 68 with awareness and service delivery. Faculty members, on the other hand, were chosen by means of Taro Yamane formula so that each of the participants had an equal chance of being selected. Out of 266 faculty members from the 2 school, 137 participated, thus eliminating selection bias and giving greater reliability and generalizability of the findings.

The researcher first obtained ethical clearance from the Lourdes College Research Ethics Committee. Subsequently, formal letters were sent to the Presidents of selected higher education institutions to request permission to conduct the study among librarians and faculty members. Questionnaires were distributed in print or through an online survey platform, after obtaining the informed consent. Subsequently, the collected data were arranged, coded, and analyzed to facilitate understanding of the results.

The questionnaire underwent validation by research experts prior to implementation to ensure its suitability and effectiveness. Kothari (2004) emphasized that instruments should be reviewed by experts to ensure they measure what they intend to measure. After their comments and suggestions were sought, pilot test was conducted with 15 faculty member and 15 librarians to determine its internal consistency. Cronbach's alpha was used to test its reliability. For reliability, a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.70 or higher would be aimed for, indicating strong internal consistency among the questionnaire items. Hair et al. (2010) stated that Cronbach's alpha 0.70 or 70 higher is considered acceptable for reliability.

The table presents the Cronbach's alpha values for all key constructs in the study, demonstrating very high internal consistency across all dimensions (ranging from 0.951 to 0.994). These values surpass the commonly accepted reliability threshold of 0.70, indicating that the survey items consistently and reliably measure their respective constructs. The results indicate the Cronbach alpha values, which indicate that the items consistently measure the construct and they are reliable if the value is 0.7 and above (Dunn et al., 2014, as cited in Malkewitz et al., (2023).

Furthermore, the results for reliability analysis showed that the regulatory awareness of librarians such as collection management, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.993; services obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.994; physical facilities obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.992; information technology infrastructure obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.991; and linkages and networking obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.968; While, under service delivery, digital resource enhancement, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.960; physical facility modernization, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.973; promotional activities, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.968; user support services, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.984; resource diversification, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.976; and integrated access systems, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.954; Subsequently, under faculty library utilization, curriculum enrichment, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.976; resource 71 diversification, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.969; resource diversification, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.976; and resource diversification, obtained a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.976; Thus, with the above result, the reliability test results of the instruments revealed that all variables were all deemed reliable.

For quantitative analysis, the participants' responses on Faculty Utilization of Library Services for Instructional Enhancement were measured using a 5-point Likert scale. The following are the basis for interpretation of data: For Level of librarians' regulatory awareness of CMO No. 22 series of 2021 4.51–5.00 Strongly Aware / Fully Implemented (Very High), 3.51–4.50 Aware / Implemented (High), 2.51–3.50 Moderately Aware / Partially Implemented (Moderate), 1.51–2.50 Slightly Aware / Minimally Implemented (Low), and 1.00–1.50 Not Aware / Not Implemented (Very Low). Moreover, for the Service Delivery Implementation, the scoring procedure guided the researcher in interpreting the data: 4.51–5.00 Very Highly Implemented (Very High), 3.51–4.50 Highly Implemented (High), 2.51–3.50 Moderately Implemented (Moderate), 1.51–2.50 Slightly Implemented (Low), and 1.00–1.50 Not Implemented/Absent (Very Low). Furthermore, for the Faculty

Utilization for Instructional Enhancement, 4.51–5.00 Always (Very High), 3.51–4.50 Often (High), 2.51–3.50 Sometimes (Moderate), 1.51–2.50 Rarely (Low), and 1.00–1.50 Never (Very Low).

The study used descriptive statistics (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) for Research Questions 1, 2 and 3 employed descriptive statistics such as frequency, 74 percentage, mean, and standard deviations to describe the extent of librarians’ regulatory awareness and service implementation among academic librarians and faculty members. For Research Question 4, it employed Pearson r and Spearman’s Rho. to test the significant relationship among variables. These tools were used to examine the relationship between librarians' regulatory awareness of CMO No. 22 series of 2021, service enhancement, and faculty utilization of library services for instructional support. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane formula to ensure representation from public and private higher education institutions in Surigao Del Norte, resulting in 20 librarians and 137 faculty members. Lastly, For Research Question 5, t-Test for independent samples independent to determine whether there is a significant difference in the extent of service delivery implementation differs when grouped according to the type of institution.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1. What is the librarians’ level of regulatory awareness in terms of the following: Collection Management, Services, Physical Facilities, Information Technology Infrastructure; and Linkages and Networking?

Table 1 demonstrates the participants’ summary of regulatory awareness. As displayed in Table 6, the librarians exhibited a very high level of regulatory awareness across all major dimensions of library operations with an overall mean of 4.73 and standard deviation of 0.35. It indicates strong compliance with established library standards, supporting effective and consistent service delivery. This suggests that librarians are well prepared to manage resources, services, and facilities in line with institutional and regulatory requirements. The slightly lower mean in linkages and networking implies an opportunity to further enhance external collaborations.

Table 1 - Summary Table of the Participants’ Regulatory Awareness

Dimensions of Regulatory Awareness	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Collection Management	4.78	Very High	0.39
Services	4.81	Very High	0.32
Physical Facilities	4.77	Very High	0.36
Information Technology Infrastructure	4.73	Very High	0.36
Linkages and Networking	4.58	Very High	0.49
Overall Regulatory Awareness	4.73	Very High	0.35

Research Question 2. To what extent have academic libraries undertaken service Delivery Implementation in the following areas: Digital resource enhancement, Physical facility modernization, Promotional activities, User support services, Resource diversification; and Integrated access systems?

Table 2 reveals the participants' summary of service delivery implementation undertaken of the academic librarians in terms of Digital resource enhancement physical facility modernization, promotional activities, user support services, resource diversification, and integrated access systems. As shown in Table, the overall *mean of 4.35 (SD = 0.49)* reflects a *high* level of service delivery implementation, suggesting a high degree of implementation of service delivery among academic librarians. It can be seen that academic librarians have made concerted efforts to promote various aspects of library management in line with current trends.

Table 2 - Summary Table of Participants' Service Delivery Implementation

Dimensions of Service Delivery Implementation	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Digital resource enhancement	4.36	High	0.42
Physical facility modernization	4.13	High	0.79
Promotional activities	4.49	High	0.48
User support services	4.50	High	0.47
Resource diversification	4.35	High	0.69
Integrated access systems	4.43	High	0.55
Overall Service Delivery Implementation	4.35	High	0.49

Research Question 3. To what extent do faculty members utilize library services to support their instructional processes, specifically in terms of: Research and academic support, Instructional Enhancement, Professional Development; and Technology and Digital Services?

Table 3 presents the participants' summary utilization of library services for instructional enhancement. As illustrated in Table 18, the utilization rate of library services by faculty members for instructional enhancement is provided in terms of four major dimensions. According to the analysis of the findings, the average score was found to be 3.46 (SD = 0.99) classified as Moderate. It can therefore be concluded that even though library services are used effectively to enhance faculty members' instructional processes, other dimensions such as research support, professional development, and technology-based services have not been maximized.

Table 3 - Summary Table of Utilization of Library Services

Dimensions of Utilization of Library Services	Mean	Interpretation	SD
Research and academic support	3.39	Moderate	1.05
Instructional Enhancement	3.78	High	0.94
Professional Development	3.48	Moderate	1.13
Technology and Digital Services	3.21	Moderate	1.16
Overall Utilization of Library Services	3.46	Moderate	0.99

Research Question 4. Are the librarians' level of regulatory awareness significantly associated with their service delivery implementation?

Ho1. The librarians' level of regulatory awareness is not significantly associated with their service delivery implementation.

Ho2. The faculty members' utilization of library services does not significantly differ considering the level of the libraries' service delivery implementation.

Ho3. The faculty members' utilization of library services does not significantly differ considering the type of their institution.

Table 4 illustrates the correlation results of the librarians' regulatory awareness and their service delivery implementation. The results revealed that there were significant positive correlations between several dimensions, particularly between *Information Technology Infrastructure and Promotional Activities* ($r = 0.670, p = 0.001$), *Information Technology Infrastructure and Digital Resource Enhancement* ($r = 0.641, p = 0.002$), and *Collection Management and Digital Resource Enhancement* ($r = 0.635, p = 0.003$). Hence, Ho_1 is rejected (the librarians' level of regulatory awareness is not significantly associated with their service delivery implementation).

Consequently, the first null hypothesis is rejected. These findings imply that as librarians' understanding and awareness of CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) standards and institutional regulations increase especially in the area of technology infrastructure their capacity to implement innovative and user-centered service delivery also improves. These findings suggest that higher levels of regulatory awareness among librarians are associated with better implementation of these service areas. Consequently, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between librarians' regulatory awareness and service enhancement implementation is rejected for these dimensions.

Okwu and Nsirim (2023) stated that librarians who are well-informed about regulatory standards integrate digital systems, promote access to online resources, and align operations with national educational goals. Similarly, Owolabi et al. (2024) highlighted that digital resource enhancement is associated with regulatory compliance and modernization initiatives, ensuring accessibility, data privacy, and equitable information access. Overall, these results indicate that regulatory awareness plays a role in shaping librarians' performance, particularly in technological integration, digital resource management, and promotional initiatives. However, weaker correlations in facility

modernization and networking indicate the need for institutional investment, administrative support, and policy enforcement to translate awareness into operational improvements. This research result agrees with Eke et al. (2025) that compliance-based awareness should be complemented by infrastructure and resources to effect successful service innovation in academic libraries.

Table 4 - Correlation Results of the Librarians' Regulatory Awareness and their Service Delivery Implementation

Service Delivery Implementation	Measures	Collection Mgt.	Services	Physical Facilities	Info Tech Infrastructure	Linkages & Networking
Digital resource enhancement	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.635** .003	.513* .021	.612** .004	.641** .002	.556* .011
Physical facility modernization	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.227 .336	.099 .677	.179 .451	.228 .333	.116 .627
Promotional Activities	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.605** .005	.531* .016	.595** .006	.670** .001	.429 .059
User support services	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.574** .008	.510* .022	.542* .014	.575** .008	.561* .010
Resource Diversification	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.297 .203	.216 .360	.261 .267	.317 .173	.183 .440
Integrated Access System	Correlation Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	.431 .058	.315 .176	.359 .120	.538* .015	.302 .196

**significant at 0.05 level

*significant at 0.01 level

Research Question 5. Does the faculty members' utilization of library services significantly differ considering the level of the libraries' service delivery implementation and the type of their institution?

Table 5 presents the analysis of variance (ANOVA) results on the faculty members' utilization of library services considering the level of the libraries' service delivery implementation. The null hypothesis (Ho2) is that there is no significant difference in the faculty members' utilization of library services when grouped according to the level of the libraries' service delivery implementation. The findings reveal that among the four dimensions, only Instructional Enhancement showed a statistically significant difference with an F-value of 3.08, p = .049, and an effect size ($\eta^2 = .044$), which denotes a small effect. Hence, for this dimension the null hypothesis is rejected. This result indicates that faculty use of library services for instruction varies based on the extent of service delivery

implementation. In contrast, Research and Academic Support ($p = .443$), Professional Development ($p = .414$), Technology and Digital Services ($p = .068$), and the Overall Utilization ($p = .183$) exhibit significant differences. Hence, for the overall utilization and these specific areas, the second null hypothesis is not rejected, suggesting a relatively consistent use of these services regardless of the level of service delivery implementation.

Table 5 Analysis of Variance of Faculty Members' Utilization of Library Services Considering the Libraries' Service Delivery Implementation

Utilization of Library Services	Level of Libraries' Service Delivery Utilization			F(3,134)	p	η^2
	Very High	High	Moderate			
Research and academic support	3.32	3.34	3.66	.820	.443	.012
Instructional Enhancement	3.71	3.69	4.24	3.08*	.049	.044
Professional Development	3.34	3.45	3.76	.888	.414	.013
Technology and Digital Services	2.81	3.25	3.58	2.74	.068	.039
Overall	3.29	3.43	3.81	1.72	.183	.025

Note. η^2 = effect size. Post-hoc test used is Tukey's. Effect size interpretation: 0.01 to 0.05 is small, 0.06 to 0.13 is medium, above or equal 0.14 is large.

*significant at 0.05 level

Table 6 presents the results of the independent samples t-test comparing the utilization of library services between faculty members from private and public higher education institutions. The results indicate that faculty members from private institutions ($M = 4.24$, $SD = 0.69$), interpreted as *High*, reported significantly higher utilization of library services than those from public institutions ($M = 3.29$, $SD = 0.97$), interpreted as *Moderate*. The difference between the two groups was statistically significant, $t(48) = 5.74$, $p < .01$, with a large effect size (Cohen's $d = 1.02$). This shows a significant relationship between the type of institution and the level of faculty usage of library facilities, with higher usage in private institutions. Thus, it emphasizes the need to improvement the facilities of public institutions.

Table 6 Independent Samples t-test for Private and Public Institutions

Group	M	Interpretation	SD	t(48)	p	Cohen's d
Private School (n = 25)	4.24	High	.685	5.74**	0.000	1.02
Public Schools (n = 112)	3.29	Moderate	.968			

**significant at 0.01 two-tailed alpha level. M = mean, SD = standard deviation, t = t statistic, p = probability value, Cohen's d = effect size

The large effect size indicated by Cohen's $d = 1.02$ means that there is a huge gap between the groups, and thus the difference is important. The high level associated with private schools while moderate with public schools 132 confirms the huge difference, meaning that the private schools might be more resourceful than the public schools in regard to the variable measured. Seno-Sanoria (2025) found that private universities in the Philippines usually provide better resource allocation and faculty support, making research and teaching more effective. Similarly, Ardyawin et al. (2025) noted that private universities receive more support from their institutions regarding the enhancement of their instructions as well as the integration of technologies to facilitate learning, resulting in improved satisfaction of the teachers. The large effect size (Cohen's d) is confirmed in previous literature where it was shown that differences in financing, faculty support, and availability of technological facilities play a significant role in the performance of schools (Lindvall, 2025).

Conclusions

The results emphasize the need for librarians' regulatory awareness and implementation of service delivery to facilitate effective, quality, and responsive academic library services. The very high regulatory awareness in collection management, services, physical facilities, information technology infrastructure, and links, implying compliance with institutional and national standards. Similarly, the very high service delivery implementation implies that librarians modernize through promotional initiatives and integrated access systems. Thus, these findings imply that librarians incorporate innovations aligned with educational and technological advancements to meet the demands of faculty and students.

On the contrary, the medium level of utilization by faculty indicates that despite the development and resourceful libraries, improvement is needed. Faculty primarily use library services for instructional enhancement, indicating opportunities for increased engagement in research, professional development, and digital activities. Based on Systems Theory, the findings reveal that libraries function as a system where regulatory awareness, service delivery, and utilization coordinate to achieve effectiveness. Thus, when these elements align, libraries function as academic systems.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn in the study, the researcher recommends the following to: That School Administrators may provide greater institutional support to promote the growth and development of the library by maintaining continual investments in digital technology, collection management (both print and electronic), and facility improvements. Additionally, collaboration among librarians and academic faculty could be promoted to realize full value from library services. Moreover, That Librarians may regularly organize orientations and training sessions for academic faculty to enable them to make use of the various print and digital resources that support teaching, research, and professional development; may consider enhancing the service delivery program through initiatives such as user services, promotional activities, and integration; may also formulate an information technology strategy that would involve system enhancement, procurement of computing equipment, and ICT training; may facilitate collaborative undertakings including librarian-faculty collaborative research projects, resource assessment panels, and academic discussions for continuous involvement and mutual accountability in the creation of academic resources; public universities must improve their digital capabilities and increase collaboration between librarians and faculty members to mitigate the disparity in the use of library services for instruction purposes. It is imperative that public universities do so since private universities have a much higher level of faculty involvement, probably owing to ample resources. Lastly, Future Researchers. That they may consider examining other factors like library management strategies, patron satisfaction, digital competence, and the influence of new technologies on library services efficiency. Further studies may also consider comparative analyses among different academic institutions to provide a broader understanding of library modernization and user engagement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The principles in the Belmont Report were strictly followed. The principle of respect for persons was observed through informed consent, voluntary participation, and confidentiality. The principle of beneficence was upheld by minimizing risk and maximizing potential benefits for improved library and teaching services. Likewise, justice was practiced through fair selection of participants. The study adhered to the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Moreover, anonymity was ensured by coding data and participants' identities. Personal responses were kept confidential, and results were aggregated and presented as statistical data. Computer-based data were stored in encrypted files, while paper-based data were kept in a locked filing cabinet, accessible only to the researcher. Following the research, data were stored for an appropriate period and then destroyed through deletion and shredding. Participants were informed of their right to terminate participation at any point, and data would be discarded accordingly.

Likewise, the threat of fatigue during the survey process was minimized by using easy-to-understand questionnaires, completed within 15 to 20 minutes. It was clarified that the

survey aimed to general practices, not individual performances. Furthermore, participants could include partially completed questionnaires in data analysis after withdrawal from the study.

Lastly, while there was no direct financial benefit for the participants, they benefited from the research findings shared through reporting. The findings to provide evidence-based recommendations to improve better service delivery in libraries, enhance librarian and faculty relationships, and ensure compliance with CHED Memorandum Order No. 22, Series of 2021.

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